

Ion-electron and ion-atom reactions of gas-phase proteins in omnitrap

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Nobel prize in Medicine or Physiology 2018

Tasuku Honjo

James Allison

What for?...

Unlike more traditional forms of cancer treatment that directly target cancer cells, **Allison and Honjo** **figured out how to help the patient's own immune system tackle the cancer more quickly.**

Imagine the world

where all human diseases are cured by body's own immune system...

But what is immune system?

The main function of the humoral **immune system** is the production of **antibodies**.

An **antibody** (Ab), or immunoglobulin (Ig), is a large, Y-shaped protein produced mainly by plasma cells that is used by the immune system to neutralize pathogens such as pathogenic bacteria and viruses.

Ig structure and polyclonal complexity

Ig concentration in blood: 7 -15 g/L (15-25% of all protein content)

Theoretically 10^{15} different antigen binding sites (but more likely 10^{13})

C= conserved

V=variable <40

D=diversity <23

J=Joining <6

V(D)J-recombination

Heavy chain (VDJ) / Light chains - κ / λ , (VJ)

Monomer
IgD, IgE, IgG

Dimer
IgA

Pentamer
IgM

Why is the polyclonal antibody repertoire (“Ig[G]ome”) of interest?

Old paradigm

“Antigen specificity is determined by a completely random process which will result in unique antigen binding complementary determining regions (CDRs) in antibodies (of similar target) in different individuals”

Emerging paradigm

“Ig with particular antigen specificity will show a level of inter-individual sequence homology”

To know how immune system works, one needs to sequence the Ig-ome

References

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 5. Thurgood LA et al. (2013) Clin Exp Immunol 174, 237-44
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GRANT: H2020- FETOPEN - Future and Emerging Technologies (FET) – Open research and innovation actions

The TopSpec EU project (2019-21) will develop a novel TOP-down tandem mass SPECTrometry (MS/MS) platform for Ig analysis.

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TopSpec envisioned

- 1)** Clinical sample; **2)** IgG (protein) enrichment
- 3)** pi-Trap online pi fractionator; /desalinicator/buffer exchanger
- 4)** Modified Q-Exactive HF X ultra-high-resolution FT mass spectrometer
- 5)** FTMS Booster – high-performance data acquisition and real-time big data processing system
- 6)** Omnitrap – all-inclusive MS/MS device for protein sequencing; **7)** ion mobility device

Aim: *Hydrogen-abundant radical cations* without charge reduction

Omnitrap – Q Exactive Combination

Omnitrap-Orbitrap activation network

Omnitrap is fully digital

All potentials are well defined most of the time

oscilloscope
traces

User Interface

Omni Trap Control v1.2
⏏

Connection

Port:

Omni Trap Control

RF Disabled

Current function file: [temp_1.fun](#)

Power control

Turbo Pump 1 Switching DCs

Turbo Pump 2 Molecular Beam

RF Drive EI Source

Pulse Valves RF PSU

TurboBack Purge Valve Rotary

Electron Ionization

Fil. Current [A] 0.00 Fil. Potential / E1 -0.00

Lens E2 +0.00 Lens E3 +0.00 Skimmer Lens +0.00

Tantalum Cavity

Fil. Current [A] 0.00 Fil. Potential -0.00

Cavity +0.00 Cavity Lens +0.00 Skimmer Lens +0.00

Pressures

Hex IonGuide Mks925_12010

Omni Trap Mks925_12010

Omni Function Pool

Omni DC States Pool

#	Function	Duration [us]	Exp. Time [ms]
4	Gas Pulse 2	1	1001
5	Isolation waveform ...	Set	1001
6	Dipolar Excitation	Set	1003.56
7	Trigger In	Set	1004.56
8	Digital RF [KHz]	1	1004.56
9	Deflect electrons	Set	1004.56
10	Inject / Normal (q5)	->	2004.56
11	Lift to react (q5)	->	2004.56
12	Transfer to Store (q8)	->	2004.56
13	Transfer to Eject (q2)	->	2004.56
14	Eject to HCD cell	->	2004.56
15	Trigger In	Set	2004.56
16	Dipolar Excitation	Set	2004.56
17	Gas Pulse 1	1	2005.56
18	Gas Pulse 2	1	2005.56
19	Delay	1	2005.56
20	Isolation Resolv. DC...	->	2005.561
21	User Defined 1	->	2005.561
22	User Defined 2	->	2005.561
23	Digital RF [KHz]	1	2005.561
24	Trigger In	Set	2005.561
25	Deflect electrons	Set	2005.561
26	Gas Pulse 2	1	2006.561
27	Gas Pulse 1	1	2006.561
28	Delay	1	2006.561
29	Delay	1	2006.562
30	Dipolar Excitation	Set	2006.563
31	User Defined 3	->	2007.563
32	Deflect electrons	Set	2007.563
33	Isolation waveform ...	Set	2008.563
34	Eject to HCD cell	->	2011.123
35	Inject / Normal (q5)	->	2011.123
36	Gas Pulse 1	1	2011.123
37	Eject to HCD cell	->	2011.123

Repeat from: 1 step to: 37 step 2 times

Omni Voltage Profiles

2004.56ms - 2004.56ms

	L3	q9	q8	q7	q6	q5	q4	q3	q2	q1	L2	Hex	L1
Transfer to Store (q8) (12)	20	15	10	15	18	20	22	-25	-22	-20	-18	-15	-15

2004.56ms - 2004.56ms

	L3	q9	q8	q7	q6	q5	q4	q3	q2	q1	L2	Hex	L1
Transfer to Eject (q2) (13)	20	15	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	10	-18	-15	-15

2004.56ms - 2005.561ms

	L3	q9	q8	q7	q6	q5	q4	q3	q2	q1	L2	Hex	L1
Eject to HCD cell (14)	20	15	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	10	-18	-15	-5

2005.561ms - 2005.561ms

Electron Capture Dissociation – cytochrome c

N G D V E K G K K I F V Q K C A Q H T V E K G G K 25
 26 H K T G P N L H G L F G R K T G Q A P G F T Y T D 50
 51 A N K N K G I T W K E E T L M E Y L E N P K K Y I 75
 76 P G T K M I F A G I K K K T E R E D L I A Y L K K 100
 101 A T N E C

Cytochrome C sequence highlighting c,z fragments identified in ProSight Lite.

>80% sequence coverage. Only <15% of monoisotopic peaks are processed!

MS2 – cytochrome c ECD → HAB

The heme easily captures 3-4 hydrogen atoms, but not the backbone fragments!

Intramolecular radical rearrangement

M.L. Nielsen et al. / Chemical Physics Letters 330 (2000) 558–562

MSn – IMSn Configuration

Top-Down Spectra Complexity Reduction

mobility separated isotopic distributions

Hydrogen Atom Dissociation (HAD)

Electron Ionization & Hydrogen Attachment & ECD

Coulomb Explosion Dissociation (CEM)

Top-down spectra deconvolution

